

cold water (50 ml). The resulting yellow solid was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as cream coloured crystals (400 mg), m.p. 162°–64°; gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 3.78 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 3.4 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.8 (1H, m, CH), 6.4 (2H, m, H-3,5), 6.85 (2H, d, J 9 Hz H-3',5'), 7.03 (1H, d, H-6) and 7.25 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2',6'); m/z 298 (M^+), 191, 175, 150, 149 and 134.

3-(2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-5-p-methoxyphenyl-4-isoxazoline (7) from chalcone (5): A mixture of chalcone (**5**; 300 mg), ethanol (7.0 ml), dry pyridine (4.0 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (200 mg) was refluxed for 8 h and left overnight at room temperature. It was again refluxed for another 2 h. After evaporating the solvent the residue was poured in ice-cold water (30 ml). The resulting green solid was crystallised from methanol as light grey crystals (200 mg), m.p. 143–44°; gave violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; δ 3.77 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.7 (1H, dd), 3.6 (1H, dd), 5.0 (1H, dd), 6.5 (2H, m, H-3,5), 6.97 (2H, d, H-3',5'), 7.40 (2H, d, H-2',6'), 7.75 (1H, d, H-6) and 8.1 (1H, s, OH); m/z 299 (M^+), 282, 134 and 121.

3-Carboethoxy-4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy coumarin (8): A solution of gallacetophenone dimethyl ether (1.0 g) dissolved in dry and distilled diethyl carbonate (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h in presence of pulverised sodium (1 g). The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the excess sodium was destroyed by adding methanol (25 ml). Water (75 ml) was then added and unreacted products removed from aqueous layer by extraction with ether. Aqueous layer was acidified with HCl (40 ml) and the resulting reddish brown solid was washed with a little ice-cold water, dried and crystallised from methanol as light brown needles (400 mg), m.p. 170–72°; gave red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution; ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl); δ 1.4 (t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 4.0 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.5 (q, J 7 Hz, CH_2O), 7.05 (d, J 8 Hz, H-6), 7.90 (d, J 8 Hz, H-5), 15 (s, 1H, OH); m/z 294 (M^+), 248, 181 and 180.

4-Oxo-4H-chromeno-(2,3-c)-pyrazoline-5-one (9) from 8: 3-Carboethoxy-7,8-dimethoxy-4-hydroxy-coumarin (**8**; 100 mg) was added to a mixture of sodium acetate (300 mg), methanol (15 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.5 ml). The mixture were refluxed for 12 h on a boiling water bath. Methanol was then evaporated and the residue poured in ice-cold water (50 ml). The resulting buff coloured solid was washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from methanol as light yellow solid (60 mg), m.p. 235–37°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 cm^{-1} (amide C=O) and 1605 cm^{-1} (chromone C=O); δ (CDCl_3 + one drop of TFA), 4.05 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.2 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-b), 8.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-a).

4-Oxo-4-H-chromeno(2,3-c)-isoxazoline-5-one (10) from 8: 3-Carboethoxy-4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy coumarin (**8**; 100 mg) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride

(250 mg) and dry pyridine (0.5 ml) for 14 h on a boiling water bath. Ethanol was then evaporated and the residue poured in ice-cold water (50 ml). The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-methylene chloride mixture as light pink amorphous compound (80 mg), m.p. 225–27°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1670 cm^{-1} (amide C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (chromone C=O); δ (CDCl_3 + one drop of TFA) 4.05 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.25 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-b) and 8.10 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-a).

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Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines. Part-XVI. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New 3-(5-Aryl/Arylamino-1,3,4- oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8- naphthyridines

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MANY 1,8-naphthyridine derivatives exhibit biological activities¹. Hence, it was thought that a 1,8-naphthyridine system, if coupled to oxadiazole moiety, another pharmacophore, the resulting compound might have considerable biological potency. Encouraged by the reports and in continuation of our search for biologically active substituted-1,8-naphthyridines², we report herein the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 3-(5-aryl/arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines.

The starting compounds, 2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid hydrazide (**1**), its arylidene derivatives (**5**) and 4-aryl-1-[(2-methyl-1,8-naphthy-

ridine-3-yl)carbonyl]-3-thiosemicarbazides (6) were prepared as reported in our earlier publications³. Fusion of 1 and aromatic acids at 240° for 6 h yielded the corresponding 3-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines (4) in reasonable yields (Scheme 1). The formation of 4 in the reaction

Scheme 1

may be explained through the intermediacy of 3. Compounds 4 were also obtained by the oxidative cyclisation of 2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid arylidenehydrazides (5) with FeCl₃ in acetic acid. The compounds (Table 1) obtained by the above two approaches were identical in all respects (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 7*

Compd no.	Ar	M p ** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
4a	C ₆ H ₅	265 ^a	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O
4b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	252 ^b	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O
4c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	260 ^a	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O
4d	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	268 ^a	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
4e	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	270 ^a	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
4f	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	285 ^o	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
4g	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	250 ^a	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
4h	<i>o</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	288 ^c	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂
4i	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	>300 ^b	59	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₃
4j	2-OH-5Cl.C ₆ H ₃	>300 ^b	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
4k	2-CH ₃ O-3-Cl.C ₆ H ₃	>300 ^b	56	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
7a	C ₆ H ₅	250 ^a	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O
7b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	260 ^a	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₅ O
7c	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	258 ^a	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₂
7d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	220 ^a	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₂
7e	<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	210 ^a	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₅ OCl
7f	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	275 ^a	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₅ OBr

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Recrystallisation solvents: ^aethanol, ^bacetic acid, ^cdimethylformamide.

The ir spectra of 4 exhibited bands at 1 605 (C=N) and 1 230 (C-O-C) cm⁻¹. The pmr spectrum of 4 (Ar=*p*-CH₃.C₆H₄-) in DMSO-d₆ displayed two singlets at δ 2.5 and 3.55 due to two methyl groups attached to phenyl ring and naphthyridine moiety, respectively. Protons at C-4, C-5 and C-7 of the naphthyridine skeleton appeared separately as multiplets centred at δ 8.1, 8.3 and 8.8 respectively. A multiplet at δ 6.8–7.8 was assigned to four aromatic protons and C-6 proton of naphthyridine framework. The mass spectrum of 4 (Ar=*o*-Cl.C₆H₄-) exhibited the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 322.

The 3-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines (7) were prepared by the cyclisation of 4-aryl-1-[(2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridin-3-yl)carbonyl]-3-thiosemicarbazides (6) with iodine in the presence of 4*N* NaOH in good yields (Scheme 2). Ir spectra of the compounds (Table 1) were devoid of a strong band around 1 655 cm⁻¹, characteristic

Scheme 2

of C=O of the thiosemicarbazide, however, exhibited bands at 3 250 (NH), 1 600 (C=N) and 1 220 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). The mass spectrum of 7 (Ar=*p*-Br.C₆H₄) showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 382/384 showing typical isotope profile due to the presence of bromine atom.

Biological activity: The compounds (4c, e, g, h) were screened for their antifungal activity against *Drechslera rostrata* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by the glass slide-humid chamber method⁴ using concentration level at 50–1 250 μg ml⁻¹, and for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Streptococcus albus* by the filter paper disc method⁵ using concentration levels of 50–100 μg ml⁻¹. Compounds 4c and 4g were found moderately active against both the fungi, and 4c, 4e and 4h comparatively more active against the bacteria tested.

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (90 MHz) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard and mass spectra on a JEOL-JMS D-300 instrument at 70 eV.

3-(5-Aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines (4): Method (i): A mixture of 1 (0.1 mol) and aromatic acid (0.1 mol) was heated at 240° for 6 h. After cooling, the fused material was treated with aqueous 10% sodium bicarbonate (150 ml) in order to remove excess acid. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

Method (ii): To a solution of the Schiff base (5; 0.1 mol) in acetic acid (80 ml), was added FeCl₃ (1 g) in water. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h and then water (100 ml) was added to it. It was allowed to stand for 72 h and the resul-

ting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised.

3-(5-Arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines (7): Appropriate 4-aryl-1-[(2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-yl)carbonyl]-3-thiosemicarbazide (6; 0.1 mol) was dissolved/suspended in ethanol (25 ml) and 4*N* NaOH (5 ml) was added to it with cooling and shaking. To resulting the clear solution, iodine in 5% potassium iodide solution was added gradually with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted at room temperature. The contents were then refluxed on a water-bath and more iodine solution was added till permanent tinge of excess iodine remained. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water, and the precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

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Some New Sulphides from 4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl

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HETEROARYL and diheteroaryl sulphides containing benzimidazole¹ and coumarin² moieties are useful as fungicides and antimicrobials. Further, 1-dialkylaminoalkyl benzimidazolyl-2-sulphides³ and 4-substituted-carbostyryls⁴ exhibit wide

ranging pharmacological properties⁴. In view of the above observations, this paper reports the synthesis, spectral and pharmacological properties of a variety of sulphides incorporating benzimidazole, coumarin and carbostyryl moieties (Scheme 1).

4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl⁵ (1) reacted with 2-mercaptobenzimidazole⁶ in alcohol in presence of potassium hydroxide to give the sulphide (2) which underwent Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and secondary amines to give the Mannich bases (3). Reaction of 1 with thiourea in ethanol afforded 4-mercaptomethylcarbostyryl (4) which was condensed with different 4-bromomethylcoumarins⁷ to get the diheteroaryl sulphides (5). The arylsulphide (6) was synthesised by the reaction of thio-phenol with 1.

Mass spectrum of 5a showed the molecular ion M^+ at m/e 363 (20%) and this was confirmed by the (M+H) ion at 364 (100%) from the chemical ionisation spectrum.

The composition (base peak at m/e 159) was found to be $C_{10}H_7O_2$. A plausible route for this fragmentation is the β -cleavage giving rise to the even electron ions (II) and (III) with the concomitant expulsion of CH_2S . Both these ions can expel a molecule of CO to give ring contracted benzofuran(IV) and indole(V) ions respectively which is characteristic of coumarin⁸ and carbostyryl⁹ systems. Heterolytic fission of one of the C-S bonds results in the α -cleavage giving rise to even electron ions (VI) and (VII) respectively. Another probable route of fragmentation of (I) is by H-transfer similar to dibenzylsulphide¹⁰ giving rise to odd electron ions (VIII) and (IX) respectively. The thioaldehyde ion (IX) can expel a molecule of CS to end up in ion (XI) of high intensity. The 4,6-dimethylcoumarin ion (VIII) shows expulsion of CO giving rise to the dimethylbenzofuran ion (X) (Scheme 2).

Biological activity: Analgesic activity of the sulphide (2) and Mannich bases (3) was evaluated by the Eddy's hot-plate method¹¹ employing morphine sulphate as standard at a dose level of 100 mg/kg in albino mice. The reaction time was measured periodically up to 8 h. The sulphide (2) had very little effect, and among the Mannich bases 3b and 3e retained the activity at the end of 8th hour. Both these compounds showed the maximum analgesic response at the end of 2nd and 4th hour respectively.

4-Mercaptomethylcarbostyryl (4) and the sulphides (5) were screened for their antimicrobial activity against *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, *R. arrhizus* and *R. nigricans*. The free thiol inhibited the growth of all the species at a concentration of 100 μ g ml⁻¹ while the sulphides (5) were found inactive.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer instrument, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as